

Development of structure and data-driven methods for analysis and control of complex dynamical systems

Version 1

Description

Recent decades have been marked by giant transformations that created enormous opportunities in different fields of technology and science. One of the signs of these transformations is the overwhelming volume of data produced. Leveraging this data is the key to the next-generation technologies. While there has been substantial progress in developing advanced machine learning algorithms, the use of mathematical structures, inherent to many technical and technological processes can not only substantially increase the quality of the used algorithms, but also provide additional insight and give an impetus to the further development of data-driven methods. We aim to follow this direction by developing novel, data- and structure-driven approaches for the modeling of complex technical systems and using the obtained models for designing the control laws. The novelty of this project is twofold:

1. A unique interplay between the analytical, differential-geometric methods and elaborated numerical schemes, which are consistent with the underlying geometrical structure of the systems under study.
2. A systematic development and joint application of theoretical, Koopman operator-based, and numerical, machine learning-based methods within the control-theoretic framework.

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Latvian Council of Science

Grant

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Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Development of structure and data-driven methods for analysis and control of complex dynamical systems](#)

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: lzp-2024/1-0207

Project:

3. License

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Access Rights: Public

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4. Templates

Descriptions

One-dimensional crystal lattice discrete breather solutions

Numerically precise solutions for 1D discrete breathers for use in training and validating neural networks.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data is to train and validate structure preserving neural networks.

The data is generated by numerically solving a differential equation.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Numerical solution

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.npz

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The data generated is very specific to this project in terms of the equations governing the dynamical system being solved, the use of the solver and its accuracy. Due to these factors, it's possible that no such prior data exists and/or creating it would be more convenient.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data might be useful for other projects pertaining to the training of neural networks that aim to solve/learn the dynamics of a dynamical system. Also for use in comparing other models or methods.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

GitHub

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

To access the data, Python 3 will be required alongside the 'numpy' package for it.

Python

Version 3

<https://www.python.org/>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The expected format for the data will be '.npz', which can be opened and accessed with the Python package NumPy.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The license will allow easy and open access to anyone whom this data might interest.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Dāvis Kalvāns (0009-0009-2742-8975)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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